

THE ROLE OF THE NEW CORONAVIRUS INFECTION (COVID-19) IN THE PROGRESSION OF MYOPIA IN SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract. Myopia is the most common refractive error in children. The COVID-19 pandemic has affected children's health in various ways. Home quarantine and online learning during the pandemic became significant risk factors for the progression of myopia in school-aged children. A review of the literature shows that reduced outdoor time and increased screen time during the pandemic contributed to the progression of myopia. Additionally, the increased use of electronic devices, such as mobile phones and tablets, by children significantly influenced myopia progression during this period.

Keywords: myopia, medical and social importance, tablets, electronic devices.

Introduction:

Myopia (from the Greek *myo*, meaning "to squint," and *ops*, meaning "eye"), or nearsightedness, is a refractive error in which parallel light rays focus in front of the retina, forming a circle of light dispersion on the retina. Myopia is the most common cause of impaired distance vision. It is a serious medical and social issue, ranking third among the causes of blindness and low vision [17]. Progressive myopia is currently one of the most significant refractive anomalies, as this ophthalmic condition not only affects quality of life but also leads to vision-related disability, thereby classifying it as a medical and social problem [23, 51].

The prevalence of myopia has significantly increased over the past decade, with higher rates reported in Asian countries compared to Western nations. In urban communities across Asia, myopia prevalence exceeds 80% [30, 31, 38]. If the current trend continues, the World Health Organization (WHO) projects that by 2050, 50% of the global population may be myopic [12, 33, 40]. In the United States, the prevalence of myopia rose from 25% to 44% between 1972 and 2004 [25, 27, 50]. Conversely, the prevalence is considerably lower in underdeveloped regions, such as among the Sherpa population in Nepal. According to various studies, the prevalence of myopia and myopic astigmatism among young, working-age individuals in Russia, the United States, and the European Union ranges from 27% to 45%.

In Uzbekistan, myopia is also characterized by high prevalence, ranking second among eye diseases with significant medical and social importance. Myopia holds the top position among refractive errors in terms of frequency and potential complications in clinical progression. A comprehensive ophthalmological examination conducted during the 1999–2000 academic year on 6,027 students from seven general education schools and one gymnasium in Andijan revealed vision disorders in 1,242 (20.6%) students, including 593 (9.8%) with refractive anomalies. Myopic refraction was diagnosed in 307 (5.1%) children, including 129 (42.0%) boys and 178 (58.0%) girls.

According to statistical data from the “SIHATKO'Z” clinic, the following prevalence rates of myopia were identified among its visitors: 60% in children aged 9–12, 30% in adolescents aged 12–15, and approximately 10% in adults over 60 [8].

Myopia is a major risk factor for several other eye pathologies, including cataracts, glaucoma, retinal detachment, and myopic maculopathy, comparable to the risks associated with hypertension for stroke and myocardial infarction [18, 46]. Given the pathological complications and serious conditions linked to myopia, it not only negatively impacts self-perception, career choices, and eye health but is also one of the leading causes of blindness worldwide [24, 39, 43, 47]. The annual incidence of retinal detachment is 0.015% in patients with myopia of less than 4.74 diopters (D), rising to 0.07% in those with more than 5 D and 3.2% in cases with myopia over 6 D [10, 11]. A recent study found that 10% of Asian schoolchildren have high myopia, increasing their risk of future retinal diseases [58].

Two forms of myopia are distinguished based on clinical progression and prognosis: simple (physiological or school myopia) and pathological (degenerative) [16]. In physiological myopia, the eye structures develop normally, but the refractive power does not correlate with axial length. This form typically begins in childhood or adolescence and ranges from mild to moderate (up to 6.00 D) [2, 20]. Its progression usually continues throughout the adolescent growth period, slowing or stopping in the second decade of life. A second shift in myopia may occur, albeit rarely, in the late second or early third decade of life [56].

Risk Factors for Development and Progression of Myopia: The widely accepted theory of myopia pathogenesis is the three-component theory proposed by E.S. Avetisov in 1965. According to this theory, the onset of myopia is determined by three factors:

Genetic predisposition

Weak accommodation

Reduced strength and elasticity of the sclera [1]

As a result, with weakened accommodation and intensive near-vision tasks, accommodation strain is relieved by elongating the posterior segment of the eye during its growth phase.

In addition to the three-component theory of myopia development and progression, several other theories exist. For example, the axial myopia pathogenesis theory emphasizes the importance of biomechanical, biochemical, and morphological changes in the sclera. According to this theory, elongation of the posterior segment of the eye (PZO) results from metabolic imbalances, particularly increased catabolic processes in the scleral tissue.

The residual scleral deformation theory by Dashevsky A.I. and Ananin V.F. (1973) attributes myopia to accommodation spasm and increased tone of the external eye muscles [3]. The role of intraocular pressure (IOP) in myopia pathogenesis has been demonstrated in studies by Nesterov A.P. (1973) and Sergienko N.M. (1986) [6].

The metabolic theory of adaptive myopia by Koshits I.N. and Svetlova O.V. (2011) suggests that myopia arises from an imbalance between accommodation and the outflow of aqueous humor through the uveoscleral pathways [4].

Numerous epidemiological studies highlight the significant role of ambient light intensity in the development and progression of myopia in children [13, 15]. In a study by S.A. Read et al. (2015), a statistically significant correlation was found between average daily light exposure and

axial eye growth. Over an 18-month observation period, higher light exposure was associated with slower axial elongation ($p = 0.047$) [42].

The role of vitamin D is also being investigated, as it is synthesized through exposure to ultraviolet light. According to D.O. Mutti et al. (2013), increased vitamin D levels may have a positive effect on the ciliary muscle, acting as a compensatory mechanism for controlling axial elongation in the emmetropic eye [37].

A U.S. multicenter study (CLEERE) involving around 5,000 children showed that time spent outdoors, rather than near work, significantly influences the likelihood of developing myopia [26].

The rising prevalence of myopia is attributed to factors such as higher education levels, increased stress, extended screen time with electronic devices like laptops, tablets, and mobile phones, and reduced time spent outdoors [48, 57]. Myopia is more common among urban residents, students, and IT professionals, who are more prone to near work activities such as reading and prolonged screen exposure [48].

Myopia and COVID-19

The COVID-19 pandemic has impacted children's health in many ways, with home quarantine and online learning identified as key factors contributing to the increased risk of myopia progression. During strict lockdowns, children spent less time outdoors and more time using electronic devices, both significant risk factors for myopia. Since 2020, schoolchildren were forced into remote learning, leading to increased screen time on computers, phones, and other gadgets. The COVID-19-related restrictions and constant screen exposure have negatively affected children's vision, particularly worsening the progression of myopia [22, 32, 54].

In 2020, the prevalence of myopia was significantly higher than in 2015–2019 among children aged 6 (21.5% vs. 5.7%), 7 (26.2% vs. 16.2%), and 8 (37.2% vs. 27.7%). The differences for children aged 9 to 13 were minimal. Myopia prevalence in 2020 was three times higher among 6-year-olds, twice as high for 7-year-olds, and 1.4 times higher for 8-year-olds compared to previous years [5, 7].

According to UNESCO, the COVID-19 crisis affected over 365 million students worldwide, with schools in Asia closed for approximately 40 weeks [49, 53]. Students studied from home and communicated via social media platforms, leading to increased screen time and decreased outdoor activities [9, 35]. A study by Zhao in China revealed that most children spent more than three hours a day on digital screens and less than two hours on outdoor activities [61]. Francisco et al. demonstrated that digital screen use and daily physical activity patterns significantly changed before and during the pandemic [19].

It is suggested that the pandemic accelerated myopia progression due to increased near work and reduced outdoor activity, both well-known risk factors for myopia [59].

A study by Russian ophthalmologists between January and September 2021 showed that among 523 children, the prevalence of myopia increased from 8.3% in 1st grade to 16% in 5th grade and 42.1% in 11th grade, indicating a more than fivefold increase during schooling. Overall, 20.1% of children in the study had myopia. This trend is attributed to increased visual strain due to the senior school curriculum. The most significant myopia progression after lockdown was observed in children aged 6–8, driven by increased screen time and reduced outdoor exposure [5].

Research indicates that time spent outdoors offers protective benefits against the development and progression of myopia [14, 57].

Similarly, a study in India evaluating the progression of spherical equivalent refraction in myopic patients before and during COVID-19 reported an increase in annual progression from 0.25 D before quarantine to 0.90 D after quarantine. Comparable findings were observed in Turkey (annual myopia progression of 0.71 ± 0.46 D in 2020 and 0.54 ± 0.43 D in 2019) and China (from -0.39 ± 0.58 D in 2019 to -0.98 ± 0.52 D in 2020), highlighting accelerated myopia progression associated with pandemic-related lockdowns [12, 34].

During the COVID-19 pandemic, time spent outdoors decreased significantly [36], which was found to accelerate myopia progression in children [60]. Most studies assessing behavioral changes in children and adults during COVID-19 lockdowns reported a sharp increase in screen time. According to UNESCO, 1.1 billion children across more than 140 countries used digital devices for online learning during the pandemic [12].

A study by Liu Ji et al. found that children spent an average of 3.91 hours per day on digital devices, exceeding the WHO's recommended maximum of two hours per day for children aged 5 to 17 [33]. Research by Mohan A. and colleagues revealed that 96.7% of students used smartphones for online learning, while more than 50% of students in a study by Wang W. and colleagues also relied on smartphones [52].

As schools transitioned to online education, more students turned to affordable devices like smartphones and tablets, especially in developing countries such as India. The use of mobile phones increased significantly during lockdowns. The proportion of students using smartphones for one to two days per week rose from 52.63% to 68.62%. A significant correlation was found between rapid myopia progression and daily mobile device use exceeding one hour.

Psychosocial stress has been identified as a key risk factor associated with psychosomatic responses in the visual system [45]. The release of stress hormones can disrupt the regulation of blood vessels [29] and lead to a decrease in the tone of blood vessels around the optic nerve [28]. Pathological studies have revealed that acute psychosocial stressors are significant contributors to increased risk of vision loss, partly due to disturbances in the autonomic nervous system and ciliary muscle spasms [21], which are linked to worsened vision [44]. Specifically, intense eye usage combined with the release of stress hormones [55] can activate inflammatory responses and increase tension in the tissues and muscles around the eyes due to neural activation of signaling pathways in immune cells [41].

Conclusion: The literature review indicates that the COVID-19 pandemic has influenced the progression of myopia. The analyzed sources demonstrate the negative impact of online learning on myopia progression in children due to reduced outdoor activity, increased screen time, and the greater use of electronic devices during the pandemic.

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